

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Project (EA RISE Project) - 824131

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ARC	Argo Regional Center
BGC	Biogeochemical
BODC	British Oceanographic Data Center
BSH	Bundesamt fuer Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie
CF convention	Climate and Forecast Convention
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Core Service
CSIRO	Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, Depth
DACs	Data Assembly Centers
DMP	Data Management Plan
DMQC	Delayed Mode Quality Control
EMODNet	The European Marine Observation and Data Network
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDAC	Global Data Assembly Center
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
GODAE	Global Ocean Data Assimilation Experiment
H2020	Horizon 2020
MBARI	Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute
Med-ARC	Mediterranean & Black Sea Argo Regional Center
NA-ARC	North-Atlantic Argo Regional Center
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NRT	Near Real Time
OGS	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale
QC	Quality control
SO-ARC	Southern Ocean Argo Regional Center
SOCCOM	Southern Ocean Carbon and Climate Observations and Modeling
T&S	Temperature and Salinity
WP	Work Package

1 Scope of the Data Management Plan

1.1 Purpose of the data collection/generation

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is a public deliverable which corresponds to the deliverable D1.2, produced in the context of WP1 – Project Management.

Euro-Argo RISE project participates in the Open Research Data Pilot launched by the European Commission (EC) along with the H2020 programme.

The goal of this programme is to foster access to research data generated in H2020 projects, by enabling their open access and reuse. The development of a Data Management Plan is required for all projects participating in the Open Research Data Pilot.

1.2 Relation to the objectives of the project

Argo programme, initiated in 1999, has the objectives to operate and manage a set of 4000 floats distributed in the whole Ocean, reporting its subsurface properties (temperature and salinity) to a wide range of users with the vision that the network will be a permanent and operational system.

In Europe, 12 countries are gathered within the Euro-Argo ERIC with a common aim to provide an optimized and sustained European contribution to Argo by maintaining $\frac{1}{4}$ of the Argo network. The Euro-Argo RISE project aims at securing and improving the current network as well as to set up and organise on the long-term its new components.

Data from Argo floats are transmitted to the receiving stations and passed through processing and automatic quality control procedures in a few hours delay from their transmission.

The Argo data policy is fully open and guarantees a free access to the data for all interested users: in less than 24h, data are delivered to operational users (real time mode) and after a careful scientific quality control, to climate change research and monitoring services (delayed mode).

The Data Management Plan describes the various types of data produced during the Euro-Argo RISE project and how they will comply to this open research data pilot.

1.3 Types and formats of data generated/collected

This Data Management Plan covers 4 types of data generated in Euro-Argo-RISE: observational data, prototypes/testing data, results from questionnaires/interviews, and informations collected during meetings. Observational and prototypes/testing data are technical data whereas results from questionnaires/interviews and informations collected during meetings are related to personal data. Formats of technical generated data are presented in section 2.2. of the DMP.

2 Observation data exploitation and reuse strategy

2.1 Argo Data System

Data that reflects the state of the ocean in real time can only be distributed by a powerful data-management system supported by robust quality-control processes.

The Argo data management system is world-renowned for its ability to supply data within 24 hours from acquisition (around six hours for European Data Assembly Centres or DACs), under a free and open data policy.

For this near real-time data to be reliable, the system depends on efficient data transmission to shore and solid, homogeneous automatic quality control to weed out gross errors in position, temperature and pressure - a key task covered by the DACs (Figure 1). Meanwhile, delayed-mode data profiles are validated by oceanographic experts (through comparisons with reference data climatologies established from high-quality ship-based CTD casts and existing delayed-mode Argo data). To optimise accuracy, DMQC (delayed-mode quality control) is performed after a minimum of one year after the deployment, then carried out every year thereafter, with the entire time series reassessed upon each visit.

The international Argo Data System is based on two Global Data Assembly Centres (GDACs), eleven national DACs and six Argo Regional Centres (ARCs), located across the world and managed by the Argo Data Management Team (<http://www.argodatamgt.org/>).

Data produced by floats contributing to Euro-Argo RISE are high quality data and will be made available through appropriate e-infrastructures :

- Two national DACs are based in Europe: The French DAC (operated by Coriolis to process data of float deployed by Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain and EU floats) and the UK DAC (operated by the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) to process all UK and Irish data as well as from Mauritius and Saudi Arabia).

After receiving data from the satellite operators, the DACs carry out decoding and quality-control processes according to a set of real-time automatic tests agreed by the international Argo programme (Argo Quality Control Manual). The data is then sent to the two GDACs and to the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO)'s Global Telecommunication System (GTS). These data flows enable near real-time exchange of information, critical for forecasting and warnings on hydrometeorological hazards in accordance with approved procedures.

- One of the two GDACs is operated by Coriolis, in France, the other is in the US (GODAE). The GDACs synchronise their database every day and process data for operational users or research communities. The data is also archived in the Global Argo Data repository operated by NCEI (National Centre for Environmental Information) in the US.

- For the delayed-mode streams, the Euro-Argo ERIC contributes with four delayed-mode operators working from four different national institutions - BSH in Germany, Coriolis in France, OGS in Italy and BODC in the UK - who process all the European floats.

- Three ARCs are coordinated by the Euro-Argo ERIC. The ARCs offer regional analysis of regional Argo data to assess its internal consistency with recent shipboard data. Euro-Argo coordinates 3 of these centres: the North Atlantic ARC (NA-ARC, managed by Ifremer), the Mediterranean and Black Seas ARC (Med-ARC or MedArgo, managed by OGS) and the Southern Ocean ARC (SOARC, managed by an international collaboration of partner institutions, namely BSH, CSIRO, SOCCOM/MBARI and BODC).

Figure 1: Argo data flow

2.2 Exploitation and reuse strategy of observation data

The Argo data infrastructure is capable to comply with the requirements of the Horizon 2020 data pilot, in particular for:

I. Discoverability

To be compliant, Euro-Argo RISE data will be registered at the Argo Information center managed by JCOMMOPS and the data will be processed by the Coriolis DAC and delivered to the the two GDACs as required by the international Argo programme: Argo data are freely available from Coriolis GDAC FTP site (and also on GDAC US GODAE)

- <ftp://ftp.ifremer.fr/ifremer/argo>
- <ftp://usgodae.org/pub/outgoing/argo>

II. Accessibility

All Euro-Argo RISE data will be processed by the Coriolis DACs and delivered to the GDACs. Coriolis will apply the Near Real Time Quality Control (NRT QC) procedure defined by international Argo programme for both T&S , Deep and BGC floats.

Moreover, from the Argo GDACs, Euro-Argo RISE data will be delivered in a unified NetCDF data format. Integration of Argo data from the Argo GDACs is already in place with the SeaDataNet, Copernicus Marine Core Service (CMEMS) and EMODNet infrastructures.

Data format description as well as NRT and Delayed Mode (DM) procedures are available in Argo user's manual : <http://dx.doi.org/10.13155/29825> and the QC manuals (<http://dx.doi.org/10.13155/33951> and <https://doi.org/10.13155/40879>)

III.Reusability

Profile data, metadata, trajectories and technical data are distributed in a unified NetCDF format CF compliant relying on SeaDataNet vocabularies. The Argo data formats are based on NetCDF because:

- It is a widely accepted data format by the user community,
- It is a self-describing format for which tools are widely available,
- It is a reliable and efficient format for data exchange.

Both SeaDataNet vocabularies and NetCDF CF convention are well recognised metadata conventions, widely used in oceanography thus enhancing the reusability of the Argo data.

Moreover, in parallel, within the H2020 ENVRI-FAIR project, the FAIRness of the Argo GDAC services will be upgraded: interoperability of Argo data with other Environmental data will be enhanced and its reusability facilitated.

Euro-Argo RISE will thus benefit from latest advances of ENVRI-FAIR regarding these standards.

IV.Quality assurance

NRT and DM procedure are fully described for Temperature and Salinity and publicly available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13155/29825>. The quality of the measurement is documented through standardised QC flags that will be included in SeaDataNet vocabularies within ENVRI-FAIR H2020 project.

Throughout Euro-Argo RISE project lifetime, observational data will be processed applying quality control procedures (NRT and DM) defined by international Argo programme, and therefore being consistent at the European and International level.

Moreover, NRT and DM procedures for Deep and BGC Argo data will be improved (respectively Euro-Argo RISE WP3 and WP4). In order to guaranty interoperability with the rest of the Argo data, the progress will be shared with international Argo programme and only the procedures agreed with international partners will be turned into operational at the European DACs.

V.Time compliance

The requirements from operational users is to get access to 90% of data within less than 24h (idealy 12h) from acquisition. Monitoring tools are set up at the international Argo programme level to monitor the timeliness of Argo data provision from all DACS. As Euro-Argo RISE data will be processed by the Coriolis DAC, timeliness of the Euro-Argo RISE data availability will be monitored the same way. In the past 10 years, Coriolis DAC reached the 24h target more than 90% of the time.

Euro-Argo RISE data will be preserved for long term using the Argo service managed by the US NODC, with minimum of 100 years of guaranteed storage.

Finally within the ENVRI-FAIR H2020 project, the Machine to Machine Fairness of the French Argo GDAC will be enhanced, improving the availability of the data for automated ingestion processes and also integration in GIS systems. Euro-Argo RISE project will therefore benefit from these Argo data system enhancements.

3 Data sets description and plans

3.1 Observational data (real-time and delayed mode)

3.1.1 Data collected

All observational data generated during Euro-Argo RISE, including those measured by biogeochemical sensors will follow international Argo programme rules (open data policy). Euro-Argo RISE observational data will be delivered in NetCDF: this is a semantically interoperable format that can be understood by computers and enables sharing and long-term validity of data.

All data collected in the project will be carefully validated and made publicly available through the Euro-Argo Coriolis data centre and integrated in the international Argo programme. They will thus follow the international Argo programme open data policy, according to standards FAIR principles. Euro-Argo data draws on international Argo programme data policy: the data standardization, distribution, curation and preservation is thus well documented (http://www.argo.ucsd.edu/Argo_data_and.html and <http://www.argodatamgt.org/>).

3.1.2 Collection method

All data are transmitted to on-land receiving stations via Iridium satellite link and processed automatically.

3.1.3 Metadata and documentation

For Coriolis, the data service works in close association with a scientific team to define procedures for data validation, quality control, formats and products.

All documentation is available at <http://www.argodatamgt.org/Documentation>

3.1.4 Ethical and privacy issues

NA

3.1.5 Intellectual Property Right Issues

Standard observational data sets in Euro-Argo RISE are not expected to have ethical or privacy concerns, as they are open and free.

3.1.6 Storage and Backup during project time

During project time, the data storage will be in French GDAC, which is synchronised with US GDAC. A monthly snapshot is also available at: <http://www.argodatamgt.org/Access-to-data/Argo-DOI-Digital-Object-Identifier>

As a backup, all Euro-Argo RISE data will be archived at US NODC, as stated in the procedure for Argo data management.

3.1.7 Access management

The Argo data policy is open and free.

3.1.8 Retention and preservation

There is no retention period for the Argo data and therefore for the Euro-Argo RISE data that will follow the same process. Preservation will be managed by the French National Oceanographic Center that operates the Coriolis DAC.

3.1.9 Long term preservation plan

Consistent with Argo data management policy, the US NODC ensures the long-term preservation of Euro-Argo RISE data as it does for the rest of the Argo data.

3.1.10 Sharing policy

The Argo data policy is open and free.

3.1.11 Resources used

Resources used during Euro-Argo RISE project are Euro-Argo ERIC Data Centers.

3.2 Testing data / prototypes

International Argo programme has clearly defined the rules for new sensors and platforms to enter the data system and these rules are accessible at http://www.argo.ucsd.edu/Argo_Framework.html

The availability of Euro-Argo RISE prototype data through the Argo data system will follow these rules and will therefore be able to enter the Argo data system only if the quality is accurate enough.

3.2.1 Data collected

Data sets collected during testing of e.g. new equipment, or endurance tests. These raw data are typically of only engineering interest, and do not have much additional value.

3.2.2 Collection method

Depends on each test.

3.2.3 Metadata and documentation

The local metadata necessary to analyse the performances within the task will be attached to the data and will be used locally within the task. The results of the instrument tests are reported in Deliverables, but actual testing data sets are not specifically documented.

3.2.4 Ethical and privacy issues

NA

3.2.5 Intellectual Property Right issues

Project Grant Agreement default.

3.2.6 Storage and backup during project time

During the project time the testing data and metadata will be managed internally using the partner's individual storage facilities.

3.2.7 Access management

During the test and analysis period, the test data will only be accessible to the task and WP partners. When the deliverable documenting the tests results is available, then the data will be accessible on request at the partner responsible of those data.

3.2.8 Retention and preservation

The WP leader will make the final decision on retention of such test data and will ensure its preservation. If the data complies with the requirements set up by international Argo programme (http://www.argo.ucsd.edu/Argo_Framework.html) they will be delivered to the Argo data system according to the rules defined at §3.1.

3.2.9 Long term preservation plan

No long term preservation will be guaranteed for the prototype data that will not enter the Argo data stream.

3.2.10 Sharing policy

These data will not be shared unless they reach the Argo requested quality to to be considered as Argo data (http://www.argo.ucsd.edu/Argo_Framework.html) and be delivered to the Argo system and then their acces will follow the rules defined in §3.1. If the quality is not acceptable the data will be retained at partner level and only the analysis will be shared through the deliverable

3.2.11 Responsible person

The partner in charge of the prototype and performing the test ensures the responsibility of managing those data. The partner will interact with its WP leader to decide whether or not it can propose to the international Argo programme whether or not share the data through the Argo System.

3.2.12 Resources used

Only local resources. If data is to be retained, otherwise see §3.1.

3.3 Questionnaire/interviews data

To better know Argo user communities (specific requirements, usage of existing tools...) and provide them fit for purpose services, questionnaires will be edited and shared within Argo user communities.

Collection of any private data (including e.g. opinions, names, positions, etc) is to be avoided if not useful for the purpose of this study. In any case, attention will be paid to be GDPR compliant.

If such information is needed, the target of the study will be informed before the data collection about:

- a. The collected information,
- b. Why it is needed,
- c. How the targets were selected,
- d. Who has access to the data,
- e. The anonymization scheme (if any) is used,
- f. How the data will be analyzed,
- g. How the target and either agree on disagree on the terms,
- h. How the access to the data will be controlled and,
- i. How long and where the data will be stored.

To inform people about this, a template header is available (see Annex 1).

The data retention will be carefully considered: if the raw data sets do not need to be stored, they will be destroyed efficiently after use.

Data storage will be adequate to the level of sensitivity of the data. No sensitive information (e.g. age, sex, opinions, political or religious opinions, medical information or similar) will be collected.

Access to the raw documents is only accessible to the clearly identified responsible person doing the interviews or data collection. He or she can provide access to the raw information to the participant during the after-interview discussion on conclusion for the final documentation. The final results in the form of the report are public, and meant for general use in the form of a deliverable. None of the raw data will be shared in or out to the Project.

3.4 Meetings: collection of personal data

There are two specific cases for which personal data can be collected:

- Before meetings, for registration purposes;
- During and after meetings, for communication purposes (pictures and videos).

Before meetings, means of collection are mainly registration forms (online or on-site). These forms will collect personal and identification data. Personal data means any information relating to an individual, identified or identifiable, even indirectly, through reference to another piece of information, including a number of personal identification; Identifying data means personal data that compare the direct information of the interested party (such as example name, surname, e-mail address, address, number of telephone, etc ...). In order to be GDPR compliant, the registration forms will indicate specific statements to deal with privacy issues (see below the example form for the 7th Euro-Argo Science Meeting Registration).

No metadata will be created as these data are not intended to be shared in or out the project. These data will be collected, managed and deleted in compliance with GDPR rules and guidelines.

Resources used will be those of the organizing institute, and only authorized persons within the organizing institute will be able to access these data. Finally, these data will be deleted after the meeting.

7th Euro-Argo Science Meeting 2019 – Registration

This meeting is free of registration fees but registration is mandatory for all participants before **1 September 2019 (midnight)**.

Note that there will be NO registration on site – all participants must register beforehand.

If you encounter difficulties accessing the system, please contact **Francine Loubrieu** at euroargo@ifremer.fr

If you already registered but unable to attend the meeting, you are kindly requested to cancel your registration by emailing euroargo@ifremer.fr.

Registration Form - 7th Euro-Argo Science Meeting

Title *	<input type="text" value="Dr"/>
Family Name *	<input type="text"/>
First Name *	<input type="text"/>
Institute/Company *	<input type="text"/>
Address *	<input type="text"/>
City *	<input type="text"/>
Postal code *	<input type="text"/>
Country *	<input type="text"/>
Email *	<input type="text"/>
Do you need an invitation letter ?	<input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Yes
Comments (if any)	<input type="text"/>
Euro-Argo Mailing list	<input type="checkbox"/> I wish to receive general information about Euro-Argo (3 newsletters and a few additional emails per year)
Privacy policy *	<input type="checkbox"/> I agree to the processing of my personal data by Euro-Argo ERIC

Euro-ERIC is committed to protecting your privacy by maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of your personal data, in accordance with the legislation in force. We collect your data in order to communicate with you about the event, and to use it for event documentation. The list of participants will include your name, function title, institution and country only. We do not sell your personal data and we limit access to and use of your personal data to authorised persons within the Euro-Argo ERIC.

REGISTER

Figure 2: Example of a registration form. Note the privacy policy mention to be compliant with GDPR.

During events, videos and photographs could be published. To be compliant with GDPR, a form (see below) will be submitted to participants and a reminder will be done during the meeting. These data will be collected, managed and deleted in compliance with GDPR rules and guidelines.

Example of form distributed to participants regarding event's pictures/videos (Science Meeting):

PRIVACY POLICY FOR THE PUBLICATION OF EVENT'S PICTURES/VIDEOS and COLLECTION OF PERSONAL DATA : I hereby grant Euro-Argo RISE the irrevocable right and permission to use photographs and/or video recordings of myself shot during the 'Event name' (Place, date as dd/mm/yyyy) in Euro-Argo RISE websites, publications, promotional flyers, educational materials, derivative works, or for any other similar purpose without compensation to me. I understand and agree that such photographs and/or video recordings of myself may be placed on the Internet. I also understand and agree that I may be identified by name and/or title in printed, Internet or broadcast information that might accompany the photographs and/or video recordings of myself. I

waive the right to approve the final product. I agree that all portraits, pictures, photographs, video and audio recordings, and any reproductions thereof, and all plates, negatives, recording tapes and digital files are and shall remain the property of Euro-Argo RISE. I also prohibit the use of videos and photographs in contexts that compromise my personal dignity and decorum. Any PERSONAL DATA collected for registration and organisation purposes will only be used in the framework of Euro-Argo RISE future dissemination and reporting activities, if applicable.

YES

NO

1. PRIVACY POLICY Euro-Argo RISE: THE DATA CONTROLLER OF THE TREATMENT, pursuant to article 28 of the Code in personal data protection (EU 2016/679) is Data Controller –Euro-Argo ERIC, 1625 Route de Sainte-Anne 29280 Plouzané France, in the person of the Project Coordinator Sylvie Pouliquen MAIL euroargo@ifremer.fr RESPONSIBLE FOR TREATMENT, pursuant to article 29 (EU 2016/679) of the Code in personal data protection is Euro-Argo ERIC

2. TYPES OF DATA PROCESSED Personal and identification data. Personal data, any information relating to an individual, identified or identifiable, even indirectly, through reference to another piece of information, including a number of personal identification; Identifying data, personal data that compare the direct information of the interested party (such as example name, surname, e-mail address, address, number of telephone, etc ...). Defense in court The User's Personal Data may be used for defense purposes on the part of the Owner in court or in the preparatory phases to his possible establishment, from abuse in the use of the same or the connected services by the User. The data could be used to ascertain responsibility in case of hypothetical computer crimes against the site.

Information: We inform you that during the event videos and photographs will be taken with purpose of diffusion via web and press for promotional and communication activities (websites, mass media, social networks, flyers, brochure) Euro-Argo RISE: If you change your mind at any time, you can unsubscribe by contacting us at: euroargo@ifremer.fr. We will treat your information with respect.

4 Annex

Annex 1: Guidelines for EA RISE Questionnaires

Before making any questionnaires, consider the following requirements:

1. Collection of any private data (including e.g. opinions, names, positions, etc) **is to be avoided** if not useful for the purpose of the study. Make sure that all information you collect are **strictly required** for the actions described in the Description of Action document of the Grant Agreement with the European Commission.
2. If such information is needed, the target of the study must be informed before the data collection about the
 - a. Collected information,
 - b. Why it is needed,
 - c. How the targets were selected,
 - d. Who has access to the data,
 - e. Of any anonymization scheme (if any) is used,
 - f. How the data will be analyzed,
 - g. How the target and either agree on disagree on the terms,
 - h. How the access to the data will be controlled and,
 - i. How long and where the data will be stored.

This is best done by including a header information on your questionnaire. COPY/PASTE the text under the line on the next page your questionnaire and fill in the information in the BOLDED parts.

3. The data retention must be carefully considered, and if the raw data sets (answers) do not need to be stored, they must be destroyed after use. We require that all personal information is destroyed latest on the project end, preferably immediately after the conclusions of the study are finalized.
4. You must indicate a responsible person for the questionnaire who is responsible that the material is adequately stored and handled. He or she is also responsible on the access control, data storage and on destruction of personal information.
5. Data storage must be adequate to the level of sensitivity of the data.
6. Access control of the data must be adequate and clearly defined, including access policies in the long-term storage (if needed).
7. You **MUST** fill any registration information legally required by your country of operations regarding the storage of personal information. This is **YOUR** responsibility.

INFORMATION ON THIS QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire is meant to collect your professional knowledge related to your Argo data use for the Euro-Argo RISE project. As we can also collect your name, position and professional position and potentially other personal information, it is important that you understand the reason and procedure of this questionnaire.

Information on Euro-Argo RISE project: (<https://www.euro-argo.eu/EU-Projects/Euro-Argo-RISE-2019-2022>)

Euro-Argo RISE (Euro-Argo Research Infrastructure Sustainability and Enhancement) is a H2020 EU project starting on 1st January 2019 for a duration of 4 years. The project involves 19 partners across Europe and is coordinated by the Euro-Argo ERIC.

The EA-RISE project is needed now to allow Europe to timely develop its contribution to this new phase of Argo. The primary objective of EA-RISE is to secure its original/core mission (monitoring temperature and salinity in the top 2,000m of the ocean) as well as to set up and organise new components within the network, including extending Argo observations towards biogeochemistry, greater depth, partially ice-covered and shallower water regions within a long-term, sustainable plan supported by Member States and funding agencies.

The overarching objective of EA-RISE is to enhance and extend the capabilities of the Argo network to provide essential ocean observations to answer new societal and scientific challenges and support 1) ocean and climate change research, 2) climate change monitoring (characterizing climate change impact on the ocean physics and chemistry, 3) seasonal and climate change forecasting by improving the 4D description of the ocean state, 4) ocean analysis and forecasting and associated ocean services including Copernicus Services.

Responsible person for this questionnaire: [Name], [email], [Institution]

You can always ask for further information from the responsible person above, or from the Euro-Argo project office: euroargo@ifremer.fr

The questionnaire aims at providing [SPECIFY INFORMATION TYPE, e.g. technical details on users requirements] information on [SPECIFY REASON] regarding Argo data. Answering the questionnaire is voluntary and you can stop answering at any moment. The questionnaire will be done using a [SPECIFY, e.g. web-based form], and will take approximately [XXX] minutes to answer. You have been selected to answer the questionnaire as your professional capacity as the representative of the Institute you are working with.

[SELECT ONE:

No personal data is requested, although you have an opportunity to optionally leave your contact information for further information, if needed.

OR

Your personal information: name, contact information, organization, and position in your organization are stored for analysis purposes.]

All data will be stored securely on [FILL IN STORAGE LOCATION, e.g. xxxxx] and will only be used within the framework of the Euro-Argo RISE project. Access to the answers is restricted to the responsible person and the data analyzers selected by him/her. The answers will be analyzed offline. The questionnaire technical results and conclusions deducted from the results can be published within the Euro-Argo RISE project deliverables, reports and documentation, however no personal information will be published in any form. All questionnaire answers will be deleted latest at the end of the Euro-Argo RISE project. If your contact information is stored with your answers, you can also request to be

informed on the reports and documents generated from the information collected in this questionnaire.